

Synthesis of 2-(1-Naphthyl)-Coumarino-y-Pyrones

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Condensation of *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins with 1-naphthoylchloride, Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement of the condensation products, followed by dehydration gave 2-(1-naphthyl)-*y*-pyrones.

2-Substituted chromones are important because of their activity¹⁻⁸. Some 2-heterocyclic substituted chromones have been synthesised⁹⁻¹². They were found to be active¹³. In this work 2-naphthyl substituted-coumaryl-chromones were prepared from the following *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins.

- (a) 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-coumarin.
- (b) 4-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-coumarin.
- (c) 4-Methyl-6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-coumarin.
- (d) 4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-coumarin.
- (e) 4 : 7-Dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-coumarin.

Table No. I, II and III show the m.p., yield and analytical data of acyloxy-acetyl-coumarins, 1 : 3-diketones and coumarino-y-pyrones respectively.

I.R. spectra of these chromones showed the presence of coumarin nucleus by the bands at 1720, 1560, 1620 cm^{-1} , while the band near 1650 cm^{-1} showed the presence of C = O from chromone nucleus.

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TABLE I

O-Acyloxy-acetyl-coumarins

Compound	M.P.	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 7'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-8'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin	187	70	69.24	4.301	68.89	4.562
2. 7'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-6'-ethyl-8'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin	226	60	75.00	5.000	74.80	4.891
3. 7'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-6'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin	195	70	69.24	4.301	68.98	4.387
4. 5'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-6'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin	157	60	69.24	4.301	69.07	4.650
5. 5'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-6'-acetyl-4' : 7'-dimethyl-coumarin	190	70	74.61	4.600	75.01	4.124

TABLE II

1 : 3-Diketones

Compound	M.P. C%	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[8(7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione.	163	50	69.24	4.301	68.90	4.251
2. 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[8-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione.	150	40	75.00	5.000	74.89	5.012
3. 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[6-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione.	199	60	69.24	4.301	68.82	4.439
4. 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[6-(5-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione.	186	50	69.24	4.301	69.08	4.282
5. 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[6-(5-hydroxy-4 : 7-dimethyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione.	196	50	74.61	4.600	74.37	4.833

TABLE III

Coumarino-y-pyrone

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 2-(1'-Naphthyl)-[(5,6 : 8'',7'')-4''-methyl coumarino]-y-pyrone.	254	60	77.96	4.520	77.75	4.811
2. 2-(1'-Naphthyl)- (5,6 : 8'',7'')-4''-methyl-6''-ethyl-coumarino]-y-pyrone.	203	50	78.52	4.712	78.45	4.414
3. 2-(1'-Naphthyl)-[(5,6 : 6'',7'')-4''-methyl-coumarino]-Y-pyrone.	195	60	77.96	4.520	77.56	4.627
4. 2-(1'-Naphthyl)-[(5,6 : 6'',5'')-4''-methyl-coumarino]-y-pyrone.	287	50	77.96	4.520	77.84	4.685
5. 2-(1'-Naphthyl)-[(5,6 : 6'',5'')-4'' : 7''-dimethyl-coumarino]-y-pyrone.	above 300	40	78.27	4.348	77.82	4.458

EXPERIMENTAL

(1) *7'-(1-Naphthoyloxy)-8'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin* : To a solution of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-coumarin (2.18 gms) in pyridine (20 ml.), 1-naphthoyl chloride (1.9 gms) was added in portions. The reaction mixture was left overnight. It was then poured over ice containing little acetic acid. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with distilled water. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in shining, short white, needles. M.p. 187°. Yield 70%.

Fig (A)

(2) *1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[8-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione* : A mixture of *7'-(1-naphthoyloxy)-8'-acetyl-4'-methyl-coumarin* (1 gm), pyridine (15 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (1.2 gms) was stirred for 1.5 hours at room temperature. The resulting yellow paste was acidified with glacial acetic acid and poured over ice. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from 40% acetic acid in short needles, m.p. 163°. Yield 50%.

Fig (B)

(3) *2-(1'-Naphthyl)-[(5,6 : 8'',7'')-4-methyl-coumarino]- γ -pyrone* : 1-(1-Naphthyl)-3-[8-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3-dione (0.6 gm) was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 ml.) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) for an hour. The reaction mixture was poured over ice. The solid obtained was washed with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. It was crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 254°. Yield 60%.

Fig (C)

Activity : 1-(1'-Naphthyl)-3-[6-(4-methyl-7-hydroxy-coumaryl)]-propane-1 : 3 dione was found to be active against *T. Menta* and *M. Smegmatis* at a dilution of 200 $\mu\text{g/ml.}$, while the other compounds were found to be inactive.

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